

Local Extrema of apparent brightness of Jupiter and Saturn seen from their moons

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2016

An observer stays in a space ship that circles round a moon. .

Explanation: mag= stellar magnitude, °=deg, '=angular minute, ''=angular second
AE = astronomical unit = 149598500 km ,h=hour

Jupiter seen from Amalthea:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Amalthea – Jupiter in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 5h -6h	Weaker than -7.00	<1	0.001212	2.28	46.44
4.1.2017 11h - 12h	-20.31	99-100	0.001220 – 0.001222 increasing	175.85 – 176.84 increasing	46.04-46.12 decreasing

Jupiter seen from Io:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Io – Jupiter in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 3h - 6h	-18.50	99-100 decreasing	0.002798 – 0.002801 decreasing	171.36 – 172.49 decreasing	19.65 – 19.67 increasing
2.1.2017 1h - 2h	Weaker than -6.00	<1	0.002788	2.28	19.74

Jupiter seen from Europa:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Europa – Jupiter in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
2.1.2017 8h - 9h	Weaker than -5.00	<1	0.004556	2.62 -2.63 increasing	12.17
4.1.2017 0h - 4h	-17.47	99-100 increasing	0.004502 – 0.004510 increasing	172.63 – 174.29 increasing	12.19

Jupiter seen from Ganymede:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Ganymede – Jupiter in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
1.1.2017 2h - 3h	Weaker than -4.00	<1	0.007249	2.32 – 2.33 increasing	7.56
4.1.2017 13h - 16h	-16.44	99-100	0.007234 – 0.007235 increasing	172.45-172.64 increasing	7.57-7.58 decreasing

Jupiter seen from Callisto:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Callisto – Jupiter in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°]
5.1.2017 0h - 2h	Weaker than -3.00	<1	0.012599	2.33-2.35 increasing	4.35
13.1.2017 3h - 16h	-15.27	99-100 increasing	0.012418 – 0.012420 increasing	174.12 – 174.28 increasing	4.41

Saturn seen from Mimas:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Mimas-Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 14h -16h	-18.33	93-95 increasing	0.001230 - 0.001235 increasing	151.08-152.07 increasing	38.08-38.28 R=74.45 - 74.69 decreasing
2.1.2017 2h - 3h	-13.60	6	0.001252 - 0.001254 decreasing	27.86 -27.87 decreasing	37.48-37.54 R=73.63 - 73.71 increasing

Saturn seen from Enceladus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Enceladus - Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 3h - 5h	-12.95	5	0.001587	26.69 – 26.72 increasing	29.41 R=61.20
1.1.2017 20h - 21h	-17.78	95	0.001598	153.28-153.32 decreasing	29.20 R=60.86

Saturn seen from Tethys:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Tethys-Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
2.1.2017 1h - 13h	-12.53	6	0.001969	27.11-27.12 increasing	23.61 R=50.96
3.1.2017 0h - 2h	-17.32	94	0.001970	152.56-152.59 decreasing	23.60 R= 50.95

Saturn seen from Dione:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Dione-Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
2.1.2017 14h – 16h	-16.79	95	0.002519	153.04-153.15 decreasing	18.41 R=40.87
3.1.2017 23h - 24h	-11.95	5	0.002522 - 0.002523 increasing	26.75-26.77 increasing	18.37-18.38 R=40.81 - 40.82 decreasing

Saturn seen from Rhea:

Date	Apparent brightness	Phase in per cent	Distance Rhea-Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
1.1.2017 17h - 22h	-16.06	94	0.003520 - 0.003521 increasing	152.70-152.73 increasing	13.13-13.14 R=29.84 - 29.86 decreasing
4.1.2017 1h - 3h	-11.19	5	0.003520	26.45-26.46 increasing	13.14 R=29.86

Saturn seen from Titan:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Titan-Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
7.1.2017 3h - 16h	-14.23	94-95 increasing	0.008169 - 0.008208 increasing	152.22-153.73 increasing	5.62-5.65 R=13.04 - 13.12 decreasing
15.1.2017 17h - 23h	-9.37	5-6 decreasing	0.008134 - 0.008151 decreasing	26.43-26.48 decreasing	5.66-5.68 R=13.13 - 13.17 increasing

Saturn seen from Hyperion:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Hyperion - Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
4.1.-5.1. 2017	-14.03	93-96 increasing	0.008890 - 0.009023 increasing	150.50-154.42 increasing	5.12-5.19 R=11.87 - 12.06 decreasing
16.1.2017 13h - 20h	-8.70	5	0.010541 - 0.010598 decreasing	25.56-25.66 decreasing	4.35-4.38 R=10.12 - 10.18 increasing

Saturn seen from Iapetus:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance Iapetus - Saturn in AE	angle distance to sun [°]	Apparent diameter [°] R=ring
25.1.-29.1. 2017	-12.01	97-99 increasing	0.023451 - 0.023617 increasing	162.76 - 165.97 increasing	1.95-1.97 R=4.55-4.59 decreasing
10.3.2017 2h - 11h	-4.74	1	0.023986 - 0.024002 decreasing	13.03-13.04 decreasing	1.92-1.93 R=4.47-4.49 increasing

Made with Stellarium and Planetarium.